

APPROACHES FOR AE MONITORING OF DELAMINATION ONSET AND GROWTH IN COMPOSITES

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Abstract

The principal objective of this paper is to propose experimental methodology for the characterization of delamination onset in carbon fiber composite materials under quasi-static and fatigue loading. The approach is based on fracture mechanics and Acoustic Emission Structural Health Monitoring (AE-SHM). Delaminating processes in the opening mode (mode I), in the sliding mode (mode II) and in mixed opening and sliding modes were simulated using Double Cantilever Beam (DCB), End-Notch Flexure (ENF) and Mixed-Mode Bending (MMB) samples, respectively. Unidirectional and woven samples were mechanically tested and stress waves were monitored to characterize the initiation of the interlaminar decohesion process. In quasi-static tests, the critical strain energy release rate G_C was determined over a range of mixed-mode ratios. For the woven specimens, mode I fatigue testing and acoustic emission monitoring were applied to determine the number of cycles at which delamination initiates in the specimens for a given strain energy release rate, to construct onset delamination fatigue curves and to establish a correlation between the cumulative acoustic emission energy distribution and the delamination growth rate. The discrimination between noise and signals from composites cracking is essential for fatigue monitoring. AE data are usually disturbed by noises of different frequency ranges. However, achieving clear discrimination of AE emitted during crack initiation and crack growth in the presence of continuous background noise,

such a noisy AE signals emitted during opening and closing of cracks, is challenging signal processing task. In this work, we present a new experimental methodology that can analyze and discriminate between the AE signals, related to real damage emitted under mode I fatigue cracking, from those AE noisy signals emitted by the friction or fretting of existing fracture surfaces during fatigue loading ranges.

1. Introduction

Carbon fibre-reinforced composites display outstanding resistance to fatigue loading, but are susceptible to internal damage that can seriously alter their mechanical properties. The increasing use of composite materials in primary structural aircraft applications has emphasized the need to encompass their principal mode of failure, which is delamination under fatigue loading. This damage causes a serious diminution of mechanical properties such bending stiffness in particular. Many mechanical causes can lead to delamination [1]. Among these are fatigue loads, interlaminar shear stresses, applied compressive loads, defects in the manufacturing processes and environmental exposure. According to Pagano and Schoeppner [2], Raju and O'Brian [1] diverse technological reasons generate delamination in composite structure in service (cf fig.1).

Fig.1 Technical aspects generating delamination in composite structure [1].

For the cases of delamination due to curved sections, the normal and shear stresses at the interface of two adjacent plies can cause a loss of adhesion and the initiation of an interlaminar crack. Also, delaminations appear in structures which have abrupt section changes, such as ply drop-offs, unions between stiffeners and thin plates, free edges, and bonded joints. Other group of causes of delamination onset are related to temperature and moisture effects. The difference between the thermal coefficients of the matrix and the reinforcement results in differential contractions between the plies during the curing process of the laminate. The residual stresses resulting from the differential contractions might be a source of delamination [3]. Similarly, the different expansion of the plies of the laminate during the absorption of moisture might be a cause of delamination [4]. Delamination may also originate during the manufacturing stage due to the shrinkage of the matrix during cure, or due to the formation of resin-rich areas that result from poor practices when laying the plies [5]. During service,

delamination may appear under different circumstances, such as in the case of concentrated loads generated by low velocity impacts. After initiation, internal or near-surface delaminations can propagate under static or fatigue loads. Delamination growth redistributes the stresses in the plies of a laminate, and may influence residual strength and fatigue life. In addition, the delamination damage mode is especially subtle because it may easily escape detection since the delaminations are frequently embedded within the composite structure in areas with difficult access to NDT inspection. In recent years, many studies concentrated on damage monitoring of composite structures in order to assess their integrity. The detection and monitoring of crack initiation and growth in real time and *in service* is over the capacity of the most conventional nondestructive testing techniques. Acoustic emission (AE) wave monitoring is one of a limited number of methods that permit continuous monitoring of the onset and growth of damage with the possibility of quantifying the degradation of the loaded structures [6-10]. Acoustic

emissions are transient elastic waves generated by the rapid release of energy from localized sources within a material [11]. In composites, such sources include fiber failure and matrix cracking, fiber-matrix interface separation and delamination. Acoustic emission methodology uses an acoustic emission transducer to listen for signs of the formation of a crack in a structure. Abrupt internal stress redistribution caused by crack growth, liberate stress waves that travel through the material and are detected by a piezoelectric sensor [12]. Hamstad [6] reviewed the areas in which AE has been successfully used for composite studies. The present work compares the delamination onset envelopes obtained in unidirectional composites with those obtained in plain weave composites when subjected to quasi-static mixed mode loading. Different approaches are compared to determine the critical strain energy release rates for delamination in mode I, mode II and mixed mode loading in carbon fibre/epoxy laminates. Fatigue testing with acoustic emission monitoring was performed on plain weave samples in mode I at different energy release rate ratios ($G_{MAX}/G_{IC} = 0.3$ to 0.8). A first series of tests was performed, aimed at detecting delamination initiation and constructing a fatigue curve. A second series of tests was then performed, aimed at studying crack propagation and establishing correlations between the cumulative AE energy distribution and the delamination growth rate. In this study, a cluster analysis algorithm was used to classify AE signals generated during fatigue loading and a signal discriminating approach was developed in order to recognize noise induced by fatigue crack opening and closing.

2. Experimental procedures

2.1 Materials

The test samples were prepared with unidirectional G40-800 and plain weave WG30-500 3KPW carbon fibre pre-impregnated with CYCOM® 5276-1 epoxy. The mechanical properties from the supplier’s specification sheet are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 Material properties

CYCOM® 5276-1		
	G40-800	WG30-500 3KPW
E_{11}	155.13 GPa	62.05 GPa
E_{22}	6.20 GPa [25]	6.20 GPa
G_{12}	4.83 GPa	4.69 GPa
ν_{12}	0.3 [25]	0.05 [26]

Plates consisting of 16 superposed prepreg plies were made in a heated press and samples were cut to nominal dimensions [13] with a diamond saw. The average dimensions of the test samples are listed in Table 2. Each sample contained a mid-plane anti-adhesive film on a portion of its length to create an initial delamination. The film thickness was 26 μm for the unidirectional samples and 50.8 μm for the woven samples.

Table 2 Sample width and height

	Unidirectional G40-800			Woven WG30-500			
	Nominal	DCB	MMB	ENF	DCB	MMB	ENF
Width b (mm)	20	20.09	20.4	20.1	20.06	20.65	21.6
Thickness $2h$ (mm)	3	3.05	2.17	3.07	2.84	2.93	2.97

2.2 Testing apparatus and quasi-static testing

The unidirectional DCB and MMB samples were tested on a 4206 Instron load frame. A 150 kN A532-1 load cell was used for the DCB samples and a 5 kN 2512 M6 load cell was used for the MMB samples. A MTS load frame with a 2.5 kN load cell was used to test the ENF samples. All of the woven samples were tested on a MTS load frame with a 15 kN load cell. In the DCB and MMB setups, loading was introduced through hinges glued to the sample with a cyanoacrylate-based adhesive. The ENF samples were simply put on the testing apparatus with care taken to ensure their alignment. Once loaded, the samples did not shift or change position. The MMB support span ($2L$) was 125 mm, the ENF support span was 94 mm and the ENF initial delamination length to half-span ratio a_0/L was 0.5. A thin layer of white nail polish was applied on one side of the sample and 5 mm increments were marked so that, during the tests, the position of the delamination front could be observed with a Dinolite digital microscope. All quasi-static tests were run in displacement control at 0.5 mm/min. The test setups are presented elsewhere [9].

2.3 Fatigue delamination testing

Two types of mode I fatigue tests were performed on the plain weave samples. The first type of test measured the number of cycles N for delamination initiation at different energy release rate ratios

G_{IMAX}/G_C . The second type of test measured the crack growth rate da/dN for several energy release rate ranges ΔG ($G_{MAX} - G_{MIN}$). All fatigue testing was performed at 5 Hz under displacement control with a load ratio R (G_{MIN}/G_{MAX}) of 0.1. For each desired energy release rate ratio G_{IMAX}/G_{IC} , the displacements δ_{MAX} and δ_{MIN} corresponding to the desired G_{IMAX} and G_{IMIN} were estimated using Equation 1 [14]:

$$\delta_{I\ MAX,\ MIN} = \sqrt{\frac{G_{I\ MAX,\ MIN}}{G_{IC}}} \left(\frac{a_0 + \Delta}{a_{IC} + \Delta} \right)^2 \delta_{IC} \quad (1)$$

Equation 1 compares the fatigue sample to be tested with a same dimension sample that was statically tested to produce the critical values of strain energy release rate G_{IC} , crack length a_{IC} , displacement δ_{IC} and the delamination extension correction Δ . The initial delamination length of the fatigue sample is given by a_0 . Since both reference and fatigue samples have the same geometry and material properties, their G_{IC} and load-displacement behaviors are expected to be the same. The strain energy release rate applied to the fatigue sample was measured experimentally using Modified Beam Theory (MBT-ASTM D5528) as [15]

$$G_{IC} = \frac{3P\delta}{2b(a + |\Delta|)} \quad (2)$$

where δ represents the load point displacement, the parameter Δ accounts for rotation of the cantilever legs at the delamination front. The applied load is defined by P , the thickness by $2h$, the crack length by a and b is the width of the sample. Fatigue testing was performed according to ASTM D6115 [16]. A test consisted of multiple fatigue displacement blocks as shown in Figure 2. The plateau at δ_{MAX} was reached within 5 seconds and a dwell time of 15 seconds provided sufficient time to record the delamination length. The cyclic loading would last between 1 and 1100 seconds, depending on the desired number of cycles N to be applied. The second dwell time was also 15 seconds and the ramp down to δ_{MIN} lasted no more than 5 seconds. In delamination propagation testing, the longest cumulative cyclic loading time was 11648 s ($\sum N = 58240$ cycles). This was attained by applying 15 consecutive loading blocks, each containing an increasing number of applied cycles N . The difference between the delamination onset and crack growth rate tests is in the number of cycles N in

the displacement block spectrum. For both tests, the first block contained a small number of cycles N_i . Each successive block contained a 50% increase in the cumulative number of cycles, i.e. $N_{i+1} = 1.5N_i$. The crack length was measured at the plateaus in the displacement block and the load was measured throughout the test. Delamination onset was monitored using a standard 5% compliance increase method and by AE wave detection. The compliance was measured at the plateaus and the number of cycles causing failure was interpolated in the corresponding displacement block.

Fig. 2 Displacement block spectrum in cycling

Onset from AE wave detection was considered to occur at the number of cycles when an initial sharp increase in AE energy was detected, corresponding to a first significant damage event. This AE method is believed to be more accurate in obtaining the delamination onset fatigue life than compliance monitoring or other classical means.

Delamination propagation testing was performed at higher cycles than the onset testing, allowing for macroscopic crack propagation. The testing was stopped when, for an additional loading block, there was no significant crack propagation. Acoustic emission wave monitoring was performed on the samples in order to compare trends in the energy detected with fracture mechanics parameters such as crack length, crack propagation rate and load range.

2.4 Acoustic emission monitoring

Acoustic emission monitoring was done with a Physical Acoustics Corporation (PAC) WD Rk02 piezoelectric sensor attached to the end of the samples with hot melt adhesive. This sensor had a broadband frequency response between 100 kHz and 1 MHz. The recorded events were amplified with a 40 dB gain model 2/4/6 preamplifier and were digitized and recorded by a $\mu DiSP^{TM}$ acoustic emission system from PAC. The sampling period was 500 ns and the acquisition threshold was set between 45 and 50 dB.

AE signal processing was done with AEwinTM software and displayed in real time on a computer screen. After the test, the AE signals were further analysed using Noesis Software (Envirocoustics S.A.). In order to reduce the noise recorded by the AE sensor, small amounts of putty was placed around the hinges and loading points as well as on the grips. The putty had the added benefit of securing the samples in place before loading.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Quasi-static mixed-mode failure envelopes

In order to produce a large number of data points with a small number of samples, multiple tests were run on the unidirectional MMB samples. To be consistent with the test conditions, the unidirectional DCB and ENF samples were pre-cracked. Several methods of finding the critical strain energy release rate G_{IC} were investigated, such as the calculation at the points of deviation from linearity and compliance increase. Due to the non linear behaviour of the materials, the preferred method for calculating G_{IC} was to use beam theory at the point of maximum load on the load-displacement plot. The G_C for mixed mode loading and mode II loading were also calculated from the maximum load point. AE monitoring was performed on all of the samples except for the ENF specimen. A representative load-displacement plot of a unidirectional MMB sample loaded at a mode ratio of $G_I/G_{II} = 2.41$ is shown in figure 3. When the cumulative acoustic energy is plotted against the load on the sample, interesting acoustic information can be extracted from the test. Two slopes can be seen in the cumulative acoustic energy curve of figure 3.

Fig. 3 Example of AE energy accumulation for MMB loading, $c = 85.37$ mm, $G_I/G_{II} = 2.41$

The first slope is associated with a low rate of damage accumulation in the sample, detected by a low rate of AE energy accumulation. After a certain load point, the rate of damage accumulation is seen to change significantly and then stays relatively constant before the maximum load is reached. Once the maximum load is attained, macroscopic crack propagation is observed, there is a sharp drop in the load and the cumulative acoustic energy increases at very high rate, as shown by the logarithmic energy scale. In figure 4, the G_C calculated using beam theory at both the AE damage onset and AE delamination onset are compared to the G_C at maximum load for all of the unidirectional samples over a range of pure mode I to pure mode II loading. For each specimen, AE damage onset appeared at a lower energy level G_C than AE delamination onset, which itself was lower than the critical energy release rate measured from the maximum load point. This is also shown by the polynomial fits used to outline the failure envelopes. The G_C presented for mixed mode loading is simply the sum of the G_I and G_{II} components.

Fig. 4 Unidirectional (bottom, full lines) and plain weave (top, dashed lines) failure envelopes.

Since the AE signals are recorded before the maximum load is attained, failure criteria determined with AE signal recordings would be more severe than these obtained with the maximum load method. Failure criteria based on AE signal recordings could

better represent damage onset and accumulation before there is macroscopic failure in a composite specimen. Further testing is necessary to develop such failure criteria.

3.2 Delamination under mode I fatigue loading

All fatigue tests were performed on plain weave samples under mode I loading. The principal objective was to determine if there was a correlation between the acoustic emission feature parameter such as energy of AE signals recordings and fracture mechanics measurements such as the crack growth rate da/dN . To achieve this objective, an experimental methodology was developed to identify and classify of AE noisy signals emitted by the fretting of existing fracture surfaces during fatigue loading under mode I. A first fatigue analysis was performed, adjusting the AE acquisition parameters so that the AE data would be recorded with a minimum amount of signal noise. This consisted of cycling a sample 10 times with different AE gains, thresholds and different R ratios. For the experimental setup, effective gain and threshold were found to be 40 and 45 dB respectively. A R ratio of 0.1 was found to maintain a sufficient load on the hinge to keep the pin from slipping and creating undesired friction signals which would be detected by the AE sensor. Once appropriate acquisition parameters were determined, AE signals containing different levels of energy could be seen at different points in the load curve.

Analysis of AE noise emitted during cycling

Discrimination between noise and AE signals associated with composite cracking is essential for fatigue damage monitoring and AE damage source identification. As described by Weaver and Surgeon [7], the noise signals can be confused with the real damage signals. Introducing signal processing approaches to eliminate these kind of signals will help to increase confidence in results obtained by AE technology applied to fatigue damage monitoring.

AE data is usually disturbed by several types of noise at different frequency ranges [7]. The high-frequency noise is caused principally by the measurement equipment and the surrounding environment. Unwanted signals can be generated by the testing

process itself; low-frequency signals can be caused by the loading machine and high-frequency noise can be caused by damage formation such as crack face rubbing and fretting. The measured AE signals thus contain undesired signals superimposed on cracking signals. Discrimination between fatigue crack initiation and crack growth from background noise is a difficult process and noise filtering continues to be a major problem in applying AE in fatigue health monitoring.

To overcome the external noise and noise generated during the fatigue test, such as opening and closing of cracks, advanced signal analysis based on statistical pattern recognition of the AE signals was applied to recognize and filter the undesirable signals. Figure 5 shows a representative portion of individual AE signal energies superimposed on the load, shown by the dashed line.

Fig. 5 AE energy and cyclic loading versus time

Higher intensity AE signals appear at peak loads, whereas the lower energy signals can be found upon unloading of the sample and also between the load peaks. These different AE signals would be associated with different damage mechanisms, and the lower intensity signals could be friction due to crack opening and closing. The periodic rubbing between existing fractures faces during fatigue loading can generate repetitive emissions that are not associated with damage.

Discrimination of noisy AE was performed using an unsupervised cluster analysis algorithm in Noesis (Envirocoustics S.A.), which uses a K-means clustering method that minimizes the square error of a given number of clusters [17-18]. The procedure of signal classification starts with an initial number of clusters containing AE data points and assigns the remaining AE data points to one of the predefined clusters by nearest neighbour classification. The cluster's centers are updated and the process continues until there is no longer any change in the AE data pattern class membership. In this work, AE signals were represented by a set of 7 characteristic parameters extracted from the time and frequency domains: number of counts, energy, duration, amplitude, RMS, signal strength and frequency centroid.

Fig. 6 Cluster analysis evolution results of AE actual damage and noisy AE signals

Applying this classification technique, the recorded events were first separated into two clusters, the first (cluster 1) is associated with undesirable noises and the second (cluster 2) is related to real damage source. To analyze the waveform shapes and the frequency content of the AE signals that are emitted when the stress reaches the maximum value as shown by figure 6, a third cluster (cluster 3), was created to group only the AE signals emitted at the largest opening of the fracture surfaces. Figure 6, shows the evolution in time of such clusters during loading and shows a clear separation between clusters (cluster 2 and 3)

which are associated with real damage and the cluster that can be associated with surface fretting noise (cluster 1). Friction and fretting emissions are

Fig. 7 Typical AE signal from cluster 1 associated to fretting crack surfaces

therefore characterized by low-level event intensities and occur throughout the entire range of cyclic stresses when the load reaches a minimum values. Preliminary examination of waveforms and frequency spectra shows that the majority of the signals grouped in cluster 1 are characterized by low amplitude levels and low and higher frequency components as shown by figure 7.

Fig. 8 Typical AE signal from cluster 3 associated to matrix cracking damage

The fretting signals are characterized by many frequency peaks appearing around 100 KHz, 200 KHz, 620 KHz and 717 KHz. For the signals grouped in cluster 3, the signal analysis presented by the figure 8, shows that all events generated during the maximum amplitude fatigue loading exhibit similar waveform shapes and similar frequency spectra content and are characterized by high signal amplitudes and relatively energetic frequency peaks appearing at low frequencies around 97 KHz. These signals correspond to matrix cracking damage and are emitted when the fatigue load level reaches the maximum values. Figure 9 shows an example data projection in feature space, signal strength versus duration, where clusters were well separated. The solid symbols corresponding to real damage such as matrix cracks and delamination are grouped in the same cluster and the open symbols corresponding to signals emitted during fretting of crack surfaces are related to cluster 1.

Fig. 9 AE data projection in features space of signal strength versus duration.

The noise discrimination investigation proposed in this article could be used effectively in AE noise rejections and may help in using the AE technique more reliably for fatigue crack monitoring in composite materials.

Fatigue delamination growth

This part of the paper presents the experimental results and the fatigue data processing methodology to establish a relationship between the AE energy distribution of the signals detected during delamination growth and fatigue crack growth rate.

Fig. 10 Cumulative AE energy distribution and delamination growth

Figure 10 presents the results of AE fatigue damage monitoring. The results are plotted in terms of cumulative distributions of AE signal energy as a function of the number of loading cycles applied to the DCB specimen. Three stages appear in the cumulative AE energy distribution. The first stage, which extends from 0 to 1442 cycles, is characterized by very intense acoustic activity. The second stage is located between 1442 and 10842 cycles and the last stage starts at 10842 and finishes at 16244 cycles. For comparison purposes, the delamination length as a function of fatigue life is added to figure 10. Both the cumulative AE energy and the crack length curves show similar trends throughout the three stages as the number of load cycles increases. The variation of measured crack length with number of cycles shown in figure 10 demonstrates that the rate of crack growth decreases as the number of cycles increases. The slope of the crack length as a function of cycling was used to calculate the fatigue crack growth rate, da/dN , which is plotted in Figure 11. During the first

stage, the delamination growth rate is high and is seen to decrease as the delamination grows. After 1442 cycles, the delamination growth rate stabilizes. During this second stage, the cumulative acoustic emission activity continues to increase at a constant, albeit lower rate than seen in the first stage. After 10 842 cycles, in the final stage, da/dN falls to a nearly negligible rate and the AE energy accumulation is at its lowest.

Since the testing was performed at constant displacement and there is significant crack growth, the applied energy release rate range ΔG varies throughout the test. It is well known that due to the non planar interplay structure of woven fabric composites, a delamination crack will interact with matrix regions and the weave structure during its propagation under mode I loading. Multidirectional lay-ups frequently pose problems because of crack branching and/or oscillations of the delamination from the central plane. It was found that the fracture mechanics approach of determining the crack growth rate as a function of strain release rate based on the DCB test standards such as the Paris law do not apply

when crack oscillation is observed.

Finally, this paper demonstrates that the one of advantages of the AE based structural monitoring technique is the possibility to estimate the rate of damage growth directly from the AE signals without going through a fracture mechanics analysis.

Fig. 11 Delamination growth rate and cumulative AE energy distribution

4. Conclusion

This paper presented an experimental methodology to trace mixed-mode failure envelopes for fracture toughness and delamination initiation in unidirectional and woven carbon fiber specimens. These envelopes were traced using strain energy release rates calculated using beam theory equations. Acoustic emission stress waves originating from the appearance of interlaminar micro fractures were monitored during DCB, MMB and ENF loading experiments. Since AE monitoring is able to detect micro damage mechanisms that occur before delamination, AE surveillance could establish damage initiation and delamination onset criteria. Delamination growth results demonstrate that the AE technique offers great potential in determining the delamination growth rate without having to use a fracture mechanics.

5. References.

- [1] I.S. Raju and T.K. O'Brien, "Fracture mechanics concepts, stress fields, strain energy release rates, delamination, initiation and growth criteria". *Delamination behaviour of composites, Woodhead Publishing In Materials, edited by Srinivasan. Sridharan, CRC press, 200.*
- [2] N. J. Pagano and G.A. Schoepner (2000), "Delamination of polymer matrix composites: problems and assessment ", *Comprehensive Composite Materials 2, A. Kelly and C Zweben Eds, Elsevier Science, Oxford, 433-528*
- [3] T. Tay, "Characterization and analysis of delamination fracture in composites: An overview of developments from 1990 to 2001 ", *2003, Applied Mech Rev, vol 56, No1, January 2003.*
- [4] V. V. Bolotin, "Delaminations in composite structures: Its origin, buckling, growth and stability", *Composites Part B- Engineering 27 (2) (1996), 29-145.*
- [5] V. V. Bolotin, "Mechanics of delaminations in laminate composite structures", *Mechanics of Composite Materials, 37 (5-6) (2001), 367-380.*
- [6] M.A. Hamstad, "A review: acoustic emission, a tool for composite materials studies. *Experimental Mechanics, 26, 7-13. (1986).*
- [7] M. Wevers, and M. Surgeon, "Acoustic Emission and Composites. *Comprehensive Composite Materials, Kelly, A. and Zweben, C. Editors, Elsevier, pp. 345-357.(2000).*
- [8] A. Maslouhi, "Fatigue crack growth monitoring in aluminum using acoustic emission and acousto-

- ultrasonic methods. *Structural Control and Health Monitoring*, 18(7), 790–806.
- [9] I. Silversides, A. Maslouhi, and G. LaPlante, "Acoustic Emission Monitoring of Interlaminar Delamination Onset In Carbon Fibre Composites" *Structural Health Monitoring*, 12(2) 126-140, 2013.
- [10] T. P. Philippidis , T. T. Assimakopoulou, "Strength degradation due to fatigue induced matrix cracking in FRP composites: An acoustic emission predictive model", *Composites Science and Technology Volume 68, Issues 15-16, December 2008, Pages 3272-3277*.
- [11] ASTM E 1316 – 04. Standard Terminology for Nondestructive Examinations.
- [12] M.G.R. Sause, S. Horn "Simulation of Acoustic Emission in Planar Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic Specimens", *Journal of Nondestructive Evaluation* (2010) 29: 123–142.
- [13] ASTM D 6671/D 6671M – 03. Standard Test Method for Mixed mode I-Mode II Interlaminar Fracture Toughness of Unidirectional Fiber Reinforced Polymer Matrix Composites.
- [14] Shivakumar, K., Chen, H., Abali, F., Le, D. and Davis, C. (2006). A total fatigue life model for mode I delaminated composite laminates. *International Journal of Fatigue*, 28, 33-42
- [15] ASTM D 5528-01. Standard Test Method for Mode I Interlaminar Fracture Toughness of Unidirectional Fiber-Reinforced Polymer Matrix Composites.
- [16] ASTM D 6115 – 97 (Reapproved 2004). Standard Test Method for Mode I fatigue delamination Growth Onset of Unidirectional Fiber-Reinforced Polymer matrix Composites
- [17] K. Ono and Q. Huang (1994). Pattern recognition analysis of acoustic emission signals Progress in Acoustic Emission VII. *Proceedings of the 12th International Acoustic Emission Symposium*, pp. 69-78, Sapporo, Japan.
- [18] C. Roy, A. Maslouhi and D. Gaucher, Classification of acoustic emission sources in CFRP assisted by pattern recognition analysis. *Canadian Aeronautics and Space Journal*, Vol.34, No.4, December 1988.